

IMPLEMENTATION OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLE EDUCATION IN SARANGANI PROVINCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 4

Pages: 392-406

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2569

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14018756

Manuscript Accepted: 10-01-2024

Implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani Province

Edward Ryan F. Gulam, * Alma S. Hordista
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to ascertain the extent of implementation of Indigenous People's Education in Sarangani Province, the key performance indicators, the significant relationship between the implementation and the key performance indicators, and the extent of compliance of the school heads and teachers on the implementation. The researcher utilized descriptive-evaluative research design. The respondents are school leaders and select teachers in the Department of Education, Division of Sarangani. The data were gathered through a survey questionnaire. The results show that all the indicators on the extent of implementation: Pedagogy and Methodology, Indigenous Knowledge System Practices Curriculum Content and Planning, Language and Instruction, Teacher Training, Materials, Assessment and Evaluation got very satisfactory results in terms on implementation, meaning this indicates that the program component is in high level of implementation. In addition, among all the performance indicators, retention rate got the highest percentage, meaning that 100.45% of the school-aged indigenous people learners continue their schooling. It is also supported by the very low dropout rate of the schools at 0.16%. On the other hand, statistics shows that the participation rate, cohort survival rate, completion rate, and dropout rate of the implementing schools has a significant relationship by the extent of implementation of the indigenous people's education program. Based on the results, it is recommended that the DepEd must increase the involvement of community members on the team creating the teaching materials translated into IPs' mother tongues, particularly those who are knowledgeable in that language.

Keywords: *Indigenous People Education (IPED), key performance indicators, implementation*

Introduction

The United Nation estimates that Indigenous Peoples make up about 5% of the global population but are responsible for 15% of the world's poorest people. Compared to other populations, Indigenous Peoples typically have less access to and a lower level of education. According to World Bank (2019), the education of the indigenous people is frequently lacking curricula and teaching techniques that acknowledge the histories, cultures, pedagogies, local languages, and traditional knowledge of their communities.

To spotlight the global learning issue, the World Bank and the UNESCO Institute for Statistics introduced the learning poverty index in 2019. Ardington, Wills & Kotze (2021) stated that the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 aim of universal access to high-quality education by 2030 is far from being met, and in many cases is not on track to be met, as high rates of learning poverty are an early indicator that education systems are failing to ensure that children obtain essential basic skills. Learning poverty rate which measures the proportion of children who are unable to read a basic paragraph with understanding by the age of 10, is one of the most intuitive indicators of the learning crisis.

The Philippine Constitution provided the rights for its people to avail and exercise as their benefits. As it was constituted on R.A No. 9155, it should be acted upon the given provisions. Under the Indigenous People's Right Act or the IPRA law, education should be qualitatively and equally given to the Indigenous Peoples. As mandated in the Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act No. 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education of 2013, Rule 1, Section 8 Inclusiveness of Enhanced Basic Education. In furtherance of Section 3 of the Act, inclusiveness of enhanced basic education shall mean the implementation of programs designed to address the physical, intellectual, psychosocial, and cultural needs of learners.

DepEd Order No. 32 s. 2015 otherwise known as Adopting the Indigenous Peoples Education Curriculum Framework recognizes the rights of indigenous peoples to basic education that is culturally rooted and responsive. This framework aims to guide schools and other educational initiatives, both public and private, as they collaborate with indigenous communities to localize, indigenize, and enhance the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum in light of each community's unique educational and social environment. To effectively implement a culture-based and culturally responsive curriculum requires processes and mechanisms to ensure that educational goals and objectives are attained.

The implementation of Indigenous Peoples' Education in the Province of Sarangani has been frequently addressing issues and concerns on location of the school; lack of materials, textbooks, and references with Indigenous Peoples' context; contextualization, localization, and indigenization causes additional burden to the teachers; lack of expertise of teachers in indigenous content; parents and Indigenous Peoples' leaders were passive in the education of their learners; peace and order situation; calamities or disaster; tribal conflict, lack of advocacy on the part of the community, and sensitivity

Aligned with these issues and concerns of the indigenous people education implementation in Sarangani Province, the DepEd Sarangani initiated programs, projects, and activities to address these. Among these were the following: development of contextualized, localized, and indigenized materials; partnership with different non-government agencies and organizations such as Conrado and Ladislawa

Alcantara Foundation Incorporated (CLAFI), Consuelo Foundation (CF), USAID; Parent Mentoring; and dialogues, open-communication, consultations among Indigenous Peoples' Mandatory Representatives, chieftains, and local executives of communities implementing Indigenous People's Education; and conversion of primary schools to elementary schools and elementary schools to integrated schools with senior high schools to cater the needs of education and addressing the distance travelled to other schools.

Despite the effort made by the department, there are still problems encountered by the different indigenous people schools in terms of its implementation. It was found that despite the effort made by the top management, some indigenous people schools still have poor results in their key performance indicators (KPIs). Based on the data from the Division of Sarangani – Planning officer, The consolidate data of all schools show that most IP schools do not have any SBM level of practice, and only a few belong to SBM level 1. This was due to the decreasing percentage of the KPIs. Enrolment rate for instance dropped from 88% to 84% during pandemic. Participation rate which refers to the number of school aged learners in the community enrolled to the school likewise dropped from 77.46% to 74.41. Cohort – Survival rate on the other hand experience the same which dropped from 69.23% to 65.14%.

With this, the researcher would like to conduct this study to identify the extent of implementation and compliance of indigenous people education in the division of Sarangani as there is no available resource or study conducted in the context of the Province of Sarangani that focused on the implementation of Indigenous People Education. This is the gap that the researcher intends to address. Also the researcher would like to know the experiences of the school heads and teachers in the implementation of the said program. Based on the result of the study, the researcher will propose a strategic direction plan and recommend some strategies that will help all the schools strengthen their Indigenous People Education implementation and could help improve their key performance indicators.

Research Questions

This study determined the extent of implementation of indigenous people education in the division of Sarangani. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of:
 - 1.1. pedagogy and methodology;
 - 1.2. indigenous knowledge and system practices;
 - 1.3. curriculum content and planning
 - 1.4. language and instruction;
 - 1.5. teacher training;
 - 1.6. materials; and
 - 1.7. assessment and evaluation?
2. What are the key performance indicators of the indigenous people school considering the following:
 - 2.1. participation rate;
 - 2.2. gross enrolment ratio;
 - 2.3. cohort survival rate;
 - 2.4. completion rate;
 - 2.5. promotion rate;
 - 2.6. graduation rate;
 - 2.7. transition rate;
 - 2.8. retention rate; and
 - 2.9. drop-out rate?
3. What is the extent of compliance of the school on the implemented program implementation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of program implementation and the key performance indicators?
5. Based on the result, what strategic direction can be proposed to further enhance Indigenous People Education?

Literature Review

Education For All

The Education For All movement aims to provide high-quality basic education to all children, youth, and adults worldwide. The movement was launched during the World Conference on Education for All in 1990 with the involvement of the World Bank, United Nations Development (UNDP), United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), and United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). This Education for All goals by the end of the period 2005–2015, all participants had adopted an "expanded vision of learning," vowed to make elementary education available to all and significantly decreased illiteracy rates.

The Education for All is aimed at ensuring that the long-term aims and purposes of education are met by 2015. First, this includes the expansion of early childhood care and education. Second, to provide free and compulsory primary education for all. Third, to promote learning and life skills for young people and adults. Fourth, to increase adult literacy by 50 percent. Fifth, to achieve gender parity by 2005, gender equality by 2015, and sixth, to improve the quality of education. In addition, these were made stronger by the Dakar

Framework for Action (2000), which symbolizes a common will to take action. Governments have a responsibility to guarantee that the long-term aims and purposes of education are met. Its main ideas and guiding concepts include ensuring everyone has access to education, emphasizing fairness and learning outcomes, expanding the means and reach of basic education, improving the learning environment, and fortifying collaborations.

The government developed the Philippine EFA 2015 National Action Plan, "Functionally Literate Filipinos, An Educated Nation," based on the Dakar Framework for Action, which serves as the overall framework for basic education, much like the MTPDP does for the economy. The EFA 2015 Plan highlights the need of providing basic education for everyone and adding a dimension to what has up to now been nearly entirely school-based education. It emphasizes the "urgent need to respond to the learning requirements of kids and adults who have never attended school, have left school, has fallen back into illiteracy, or need basic or advanced skills to find jobs." It proposes a "viable alternative learning system" to formal schooling, which, in collaboration with schools, can ensure that "minimum learning achievement will be a reality for all Filipinos." As a result, the EFA 2015 Plan emphasizes that educational opportunities are channels of learning that can become effective conduits of values orientation, consciousness, and information useful and relevant to a wide range of social goals.

Curriculum Development discusses the enhancement of curriculum development within the framework of the new functional literacy pillars. Research and development will always be needed for curriculum and teaching as knowledge grows, social needs alter, educational methods change, and people's ambitions rise. It is imperative to take steps to include private schools, non-profit organizations, teacher preparation programs, individual professional educators and education scientists, as well as other organizations like media, advertising, and cultural institutions, in the institutional participation in the development of basic education curricula.

Literacy is an essential component of schooling. Opportunities for survival, development, safety and stability are presented. The learner flourishes because it instills human formation via the requirements of society's culture and fundamental values. The learners' potential for literacy development is limitless. Thus, everyone should access the most significant education policies and programs regardless of ethnicity, culture, religious affiliation, or philosophical convictions. Making teaching and learning accessible to everyone is the main objective of the global society. Many governments' human rights organizations make this a common claim, and it is considered a crucial component in achieving development, advancement, and community expansion.

Indigenous People Education

The National Indigenous Peoples Education Program is one initiative launched by the Department of Education (DepEd) that requires stakeholders' tangible and ongoing cooperation by using Department Order No. 32, s. 2015. The effective execution of this initiative, which aims to promote the welfare of indigenous learners, depends on the assistance of stakeholders. DepEd's response to the right of indigenous peoples to a fundamental education that respects their identities, responds to their context and emphasizes the value of their indigenous knowledge, skills, and other facets of their cultural heritage is the Indigenous Peoples Education Program.

As also mentioned in Article XIV, sections 17 and 18 that the right of indigenous cultural communities shall be preserved and developed, and the requests will be considered in the formulation of national policies. The cultural minorities will be given opportunities for educational development through scholarship grants. According to LA Torre (2016) The term Indigenous People (IP) as defined by the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the Secretariat of the Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues under the United Nations as "Having a historical continuity with pre-invasion and pre-colonial societies that developed on their territories, consider themselves distinct from other sectors of the societies now prevailing on those territories, or part parts of them. It was also referred to by Lumapanet (2017) as Cultural Communities since the phrase contains the right to self-determination recognized by international law.

In conjunction with representatives from Indigenous Peoples groups, civil society, and other government organizations, the National Indigenous Peoples Education Policy Framework was created. It is meant to serve as a tool for encouraging shared accountability, ongoing communication, participation, and collaboration among the government, I.P. communities, civil society, and other education stakeholders. It also acknowledges that education is essential for achieving other fundamental freedoms and human rights. DepEd advises enhancing its I.P. education policy and the creation and implementation of an I.P. education program as this was stipulated in Department Order No. 22, s. 2016.

According to Bartley (2017), stakeholders are individuals involved in a school's and its kids' success and well-being. They might also be collective institutions like regional corporations, associations, committees, news organizations, and the private sector. Support from stakeholders entails collaborating with individuals, making the most of available resources, and facilitating collaborative efforts to achieve set objectives. Each person can contribute for the benefit of the group. It is essential that all parties involved in the decision-making process are included in the school programs.

Lumapanet and Adoy (2018) further stated recent trend is increased stakeholder support for academic discourse and educational programming. But it is crucial to determine whether this present trend can be seen in the management of public schools in the Philippines since the launch of the Indigenous People Education Program in 2011. It is also time to investigate if the Indigenous People Education Program's stakeholder support may be used to facilitate the development of favorable conditions for school improvement. Stakeholders' help significantly impacted how well students did in school.

People participate in system change by starting independent projects from outside institutions. They are establishing relationships with institutions from the outside to obtain the materials and technical guidance they require, but they still have control over how those materials are used. The unequal distribution of money and power may be contested or not tolerated by such self-mobilization and group action.

Indigenous People Education and Department of Education

The country's ethnic groups are frequently the last to get government social and educational services, according to reports on their literacy rates. As a result, some illiterate indigenous people (UNESCO, 2006). Culture-responsive and locally rooted education takes the established curriculum's ideas and standards and contextualizes them. "The state shall establish, maintain and support a complete, adequate and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society," according to Article XIV section 1 (par.1) of the Philippine Constitution. This mandate highlights that the Philippine education system offers a relevant education that addresses the needs of the people and society.

The use of educational resources is crucial to the teaching and learning process. They can improve students' performance and interest in the class while also being helpful guides in delivering information. Materials like workbooks, worktexts, and modules are required to enhance students with various backgrounds, skills, and learning preferences (Agorilla, 2015).

Teachers are expected to adapt their pedagogies depending on their unique social and educational settings as part of the K–12 curriculum implementation in the Philippines. This is in reaction to the RA 10533's implementing regulations, which demand that the curriculum be contextualized and "flexible enough to permit and empower schools to localize, indigenize, and enrich the same" (Rule II, section 10.2h). Utech (2008) proposed that classroom teachers should integrate natural resources, activities, interests, concerns, and needs from their student's life to help them learn, practice, and assess specific skills and competencies. This would contextualize the curriculum.

Using contextualized learning materials (CLMs), students might process new ideas in a way that fits their worldviews. According to studies, students preferred the usage of CLMs since their mother tongue was there, their culture and values were represented, and their academic performance improved. According to Shore, Shore, and Boggs (2004), students who received contextualized education outperformed those taking a traditional course in mathematics.

According to research, students learn subjects through various methods; thus, teachers must support students and develop a plan appropriate for their level of understanding (Felder and Spurlin, 2005). This suggested that teacher training should link conceptions and knowledge with the shifting requirements of students.

Nevertheless, some educators appear to have forgotten that students come from different origins, have different cultures, and learn at varying rates. The fact that every learner is different and approaches learning in another way must be considered. Unfortunately, the system for schooling in the Philippines is other. Given that most schools in the nation are lagging in mobility and accessibility compared to urban areas, it is suggested that teachers teach their subject matter by how they perceive and evaluate learning rather than adhering to the center of education's common goals.

To attain equity of learning and to be suitable for all types of learners, contextualized learning entails adopting the current environment, setting, and situation alteration. This allows all kinds of learners to link their understandings to the actual context of their life. Educators should consider this issue as they move forward with teaching and learning (Brown, 2002). To properly give the lesson, teachers may use the background of the student's life as the lesson's initial point so that the students would feel at home in the classroom. Engagement will happen if the emotional component comes first.

Yagci (2010) researched grade 8 pupils, giving them concrete instructions and asking them about their opinions of definite model instructions. It was discovered that children comprehend the ideas well while teaching with concrete materials. Students can quickly connect theory and reality by using specific examples.

Furthermore, research has shown that family norms and values impact pupils' thinking skills, attitudes, and knowledge. Understanding contextualization is crucial to determining the proper method of conveying information that can improve students' understanding of a mathematics lesson because practical knowledge at this time had been built via their daily interactions (Mei-Zhao & Kuh, 2004).

Indigenous People Education in K-12 Curriculum

To answer the call, the Department of Education formulated the DepEd Order No. 62 S. 2011 Adopting the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework. This policy was prepared in consultation with the representatives from Indigenous People Community, Civil Society, and other government agencies. This Policy Framework is intended to: be an instrument for promoting shared accountability, continuous dialogue, engagement, and partnership among government, IP communities, civil society, and other education stakeholders; recognize education as a necessary means to realize other human rights and fundamental freedoms; strengthen the DepEd of its policy on IP education and develop and implement an IP Education Program.

In addition, policies were established, and these policies were anchored with the Department of Education mandate "Education for all" thus the policy shall: maintain an education statement that will recognize, protect, and promote the rights and welfare of ICC's/IP's;

equip the IP communities with the knowledge and skills needed to face various social realities and challenges; indigenous people education interventions are to be developed and implemented in consultations and cooperation with IP 's concerned to address and incorporate their special needs, histories, identities, languages, knowledge, and other aspects of their culture as well as their social, economic, and cultural priorities and aspirations; ensure the provisions of Universal and Equitable access of all IPs to quality and relevant basic education services towards functional literacy for all; adopt appropriate basic education pedagogy, content, and assessment through the integration of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices (IKSP's) in all learning areas and process; provide adequate and culturally appropriate learning resources and environment to IP learners; and establish and strengthen appropriate multi-level units for planning, implementing and Monitoring

IP education interventions.

Pursuant to DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011 entitled Adopting the National Indigenous Peoples Education Policy Framework and DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2013 entitled Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act No. 10533 Otherwise Known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, the Department of Education (DepEd) is adopting the enclosed Indigenous Peoples Education Curriculum Framework.

Recognizing the right of indigenous peoples to basic education that is culturally rooted and responsive, the Indigenous People Education Curriculum Framework seeks to provide guidance to schools and other education programs, both public and private, as they engage with indigenous communities in localizing, indigenizing, and enhancing the K to 12 Curriculum based on their respective educational and social contexts.

Aligned in the Enhance Basic Education Curriculum or K to 12 these guidelines seek to promote among learners, teaching, and non-teaching staff of learning institutions the following: Cultural sensitivity; Respect for Cultural Diversity; and Deeper understanding of the cultural expressions of Indigenous People. These guidelines have been consolidated from a series of consultations conducted by the DepEd- Indigenous Peoples People Education with community elders, leaders, and implementers of community-based IPED initiatives.

The Department of Education has instituted a National Indigenous Peoples Education Program in pursuit of the National Indigenous Peoples Education Policy Framework based on DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011 and Republic Act No. 10533.

The Indigenous Peoples Education Program is DepEd's response to the right of indigenous peoples to basic education that is responsive to their context, respects their identities, and promotes the value of their indigenous knowledge, skills, and other aspects of their cultural heritage.

Specifically, the objectives of the IP Education Program are the following: make the curriculum culturally responsive to the specific community context of IP learners; build the capacity of teachers, school heads, and other concerned personnel at different levels of governance in implementing culture-based education for IPs; support the development of culturally appropriate learning resources and learning environment responsive to the specific community context of IP learners; strengthen the policy environment supportive of indigenous people education; and address the learning needs of IP learners who lack access to basic education services.

The Basic Education Development Plan 2030 or BEDP 2030, (2022) has discussed the domains of formal and informal basic education where the Department of Education (DepEd) develops, puts into effect, and organizes policies, plans, programs, and initiatives. It oversees all public and private alternative learning programs as well as primary and secondary schools. Additionally, it calls for the creation and upkeep of a comprehensive, sufficient, and integrated system of basic education that is pertinent to the objectives of national development.

BEDP 2030, (2022) furthermore added that performance indicators are any of the various metrics that have been calculated and used to assess how well students are performing at various stages of the educational system. Additionally, they are utilized as tools for reporting on the state of the local, national, and international education systems. Three groups of performance metrics were created: access indicators, efficiency indicators, and ratio and proportion indicators.

Moreover, the Last Mile Schools (LMS) is an all-encompassing approach for schools that don't fit inside the typical design limitations due to factors associated to marginalization and isolation. Most of these schools are GIDA and located in outlying locations. The towns where the schools are located frequently lack further essential services. Indigenous Peoples' schools in the province of Sarangani were located in mountainous locations and were therefore regarded as last-mile. According to DM 59, 2019, these are some characteristics used to identify Last Mile Schools: having less than four classrooms; having temporary or unconventional spaces; lacking electricity; not receiving funding for renovations or new construction projects in the previous four years; being more than an hour's drive from the town center or on difficult terrain; having multigrade classes/rooms; having less than five teachers; having less than 100 students; and having these characteristics.

David, Albert and Vizmanos, (2018) revealed that the amount of basic education coverage is determined by the net enrollment rate, also known as the participation rate, which is the ratio of enrollment at the right age over the population of school-age individuals. Just 6% of kids in grades 6–11 is not enrolled in school at the right age, according to the elementary participation rate for the academic year 2019–2020 (the baseline year), which was 94%. However, only 83% of secondary school students will acquire a fundamental education

in the 2019–2020 academic year. The participation rate for secondary school pupils increased to 83% in 2019 from 75.33% in 2016.

Albert and David (2012) study found that boys were more likely than girls to be out of school among the poorest families. Since 2008, there has been a persistent difference in the percentage of boys and girls who attend school, regardless of income. The need to increase the family's income may be the root of at least some of this. Boys may be pulled out of school earlier than girls when the family is impoverished or low-income because they can work for money earlier in life, typically as unpaid laborers. Furthermore, David and Albert (2015) reported that 2.9 million children, or around 11.7% of Filipino children aged 5 to 15 years, did not attend school. According to David and Albert, in 2012, this number decreased to 5.2 percent (2015). The global figures indicate that the number of out-of-school children (OOSC) decreased gradually in the decade after 2000, and this fall is consistent with those data.

Albert, et al. (2018) noticed that from SY 2013–2014 to SY 2014–2015, DepED observed a reduction in the gross enrollment rate (GER) for both primary and secondary school levels and an increase in the net enrollment rate (NER) at secondary school levels. Additionally, a greater dropout rate was seen in secondary education. While this rate decreased at both levels, it did so more quickly at the elementary school level. The cohort survival rate (CSR), which fluctuated between the two levels, increased in 2014 but decreased in 2015.

Dupere (2016) has observed that the devaluing of Indigenous teachings and low graduation, and enrollment rates.

Since 2010, there have been changes in the cohort survival rate as well as the completion rate. In 2010, the completion rate was 75.1%. This increased to 78.7% in 2014 but fell to 73.97% in 2015. By 2022, the PDP wants to raise this to 78.48 percent. Similarly, in 2010 the cohort survival rate was 79.4. This grew to 81.24 in 2014 before dropping to 80.75 the following year.

Functional Literacy, Education, and Mass Media Survey (2013), 11.6% of the population finished from elementary school in 2013 but did not continue on to secondary school, while 15% made it to but did not complete high school and 20.3% graduated from high school. Although less than at the primary level, dropout rates have dropped at the secondary level. The dropout rate for the academic year 2010–2011 was 7.79 percent. In the 2015–2016 academic year, this decreased to 6.65 percent. Male dropout rates in the 2015–2016 school year were 3.32 percent and female dropout rates were 1.64 percent. The FLEMMS survey revealed regional differences in high school graduation rates. The largest percentages were seen in Ilocos and CALABARZON, at 39.3% and 39%, respectively. With just 26.4%, ARMM had the lowest percentage. The fact that we don't know much about the underlying causes of the geographical heterogeneity indicates that we need to do more research in this area.

Methodology

Research Design

This study is descriptive-evaluative research since the result of the study assessed the level of implementation of indigenous people education program in Sarangani Province.

Respondents

Box 1 shows the distribution of the school heads – respondents and teacher participants in the seven municipalities of the division of Sarangani.

Box 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Municipality</i>	<i>No. of School Heads</i>	<i>No. of Teacher</i>
Alabel	20	1
Glan	23	1
Kiamba	13	1
Maasim	14	1
Maitum	7	1
Malapatan	15	1
Malungon	40	1
Total	132	7

Instrument

The researcher adopted and modified the questionnaire of Villaplaza (2021) entitled the Level of Implementation of Indigenous Peoples Education Program in Agusan Del Sur, Philippines. The structured questionnaire is divided into seven (7) parts: pedagogy and methodology; indigenous knowledge and system practices; curriculum content and planning; language and instruction; teacher training; materials; and assessment and evaluation.

Procedure

After the research instruments' validation procedures, the data collection was followed. The following steps was followed in gathering the pertinent data of the study, and the researcher make sure that all the necessary steps and procedures were followed to inform and give due respect to the agencies and persons involved. The researcher wrote a letter of permission to the Division Superintendent of Sarangani to enable to distribute questionnaires and commence interview of the selected school heads and teachers. After the approval

of the letter, the researcher coordinated with the respondents using a letter of permission.

In the first part of the study, the researcher explained the study's objectives to the respondents through virtual meeting. A brief orientation was done before answering the different questions through virtual platform. The researcher gives ample of time to answer the structured questionnaire. The purpose of the questionnaire is to answer the problem number one regarding the level of implementation of indigenous people education in Sarangani. Documentary analysis was conducted to the key performance indicators of indigenous people schools.

Individual in-depth interviews were conducted to gain insight into the participants' experiences and ideas in implementing indigenous people Education. Open-ended questions were asked to understand the participants' experiences and idea on the best practices, challenges encountered and coping mechanism that affects the implementation of indigenous people education in Sarangani. The researchers also take notes and record the observations during each interview. All interviews were recorded using a video and audio recorder.

Lastly, the data gathered was subject to treatments. Findings were extracted and analyzed based on the results of the treated data. The results of the study were interpreted to arrive at certain conclusions. After the data analysis and interpretation, the researcher formulated a strategic direction plan that could address the different areas that could support the implementation of indigenous people education in the different schools in Sarangani Province.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were subjected to computer-processed statistics employing the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Software. The following statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the data:

Mean. The Mean was used to analyze the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education implementation, the key performance indicators and the extent of compliance to the indigenous people education.

Pearson's r. This was used to determine the significant relationship between the extent of program implementation and the key performance indicators.

Results and Discussion

This part presents the data and information gathered. This section involves presentation of key findings, presentation of computed data into table and figures.

Pedagogy and Methodology

Table 1. *The extent of implementation in terms of Pedagogy and Methodology (n=132)*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Education is seen as connected to all aspects of life, the well-being of learners.	4.63	O
2.	Education is seen as connected to the environment.	4.61	O
3.	Education is seen where methods are used by parents to teach their children how to prepare food or keep house are incorporated in the school.	4.52	O
4.	The situation of indigenous communities is the starting point for developing the potential of learners.	4.57	O
5.	The situation of indigenous communities is the starting point of developing their own views, values, priorities, and aspirations.	4.61	O
6.	Indigenous community members, parents, and elders are consulted and involved regarding what their students should and want to learn, - when and how – as the basis for identifying pedagogical principles.	4.55	O
7.	Indigenous community members, parents, and elders are consulted and involved regarding what their students should and want to learn, - when and how – as the basis for identifying teaching methods at the start of the program	4.48	VS
8.	formal and non-formal, as well as traditional teaching are used, based on the study of traditional teaching methods at home.	4.46	VS
9.	formal and non-formal, as well as traditional teaching are used, based on the study of traditional teaching methods in the community like excursions, to learn about the cultural significance of places.	4.33	VS
10.	formal and non-formal, as well as traditional teaching are used, based on the study of traditional teaching methods in participation in ceremonies with family members, to learn about rituals, associated songs, dances, astrological observations etc.	4.36	VS
Overall Mean		4.51	Outstanding

The extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Pedagogy and Methodology, Education is seen as connected to all aspects of life, the well-being of learners got a highest weighted mean of 4.63 interpreted as Outstanding, Second to highest is Education is seen as connected to the environment and The situation of indigenous communities is the starting point of developing their own views, values, priorities, and aspirations with the mean of 4.61 interpreted as Outstanding, The situation of indigenous communities is the starting point for developing the potential of learners with the mean of 4.57 interpreted as Outstanding, Indigenous community members, parents, and elders are consulted and involved regarding what their students should and want to learn,

- when and how – as the basis for identifying pedagogical principles, with the mean of 4.55 interpreted as Outstanding, Education is seen where methods are used by parents to teach their children how to prepare food or keep house are incorporated in the school, with the mean of 4.52 interpreted as Outstanding. Indigenous community members, parents, and elders are consulted and involved regarding what their students should and want to learn, - when and how – as the basis for identifying teaching methods at the start of the program, with the mean of 4.48 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, then formal and non-formal, as well as traditional teaching are used, based on the study of traditional teaching methods at home, with the mean of 4.46 interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

Non-formal, as well as traditional teaching are used, based on the study of traditional teaching methods in participation in ceremonies with family members, to learn about rituals, associated songs, dances, astrological observations etc, with the mean of 4.36 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, formal and non-formal, as well as traditional teaching are used, based on the study of traditional teaching methods in the community like excursions, to learn about the cultural significance of places, got the lowest mean of 4.33 interpreted as Very Satisfactory

For overall mean of 4.51 interpreted as Outstanding on the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Pedagogy and Methodology.

Indigenous Knowledge and System Practices

The extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Indigenous Knowledge and System Practices, Respect for, add recognition of ownership of indigenous communities as holders of indigenous knowledge got a highest weighted mean of 4.72 interpreted as Outstanding, Second to highest is Respect for, add recognition of ownership of indigenous communities as holders for their specific ways of generating and transmitting knowledge ,with the mean of 4.71 interpreted as Outstanding, Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the planning programs with the mean of 4.57 interpreted as Outstanding, Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the selection of teaching methods, with the mean of 4.55 interpreted as Outstanding.

Table 2. *The extent of implementation in terms of Indigenous Knowledge and System Practices (n=132)*

	Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1.	Respect for, add recognition of ownership of indigenous communities as holders of indigenous knowledge.	4.72	O
2.	Respect for, add recognition of ownership of indigenous communities as holders for their specific ways of generating and transmitting knowledge.	4.71	O
3.	Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the planning programs.	4.57	O
4.	Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the selection of teaching methods.	4.55	O
5.	Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the design of curricula	4.52	O
6.	Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the production of educational materials.	4.47	VS
7.	Stories, diaries, textbooks, etc., are produced by the indigenous teachers.	4.35	VS
8.	Non-verbal education materials are produced by the indigenous teachers.	4.24	VS
9.	The active participation of students and community members who serve to develop a curriculum founded on indigenous people's cultural identify.	4.33	VS
10.	The active participation of students and community members who serve to develop a curriculum founded on indigenous people's cultural history.	4.37	VS
	Overall Mean	4.48	VS

Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the design of curricula, with the mean of 4.52 interpreted as Outstanding, Identification and incorporation of relevant local cultural knowledge with the participation and informed consent of indigenous communities and elders in the production of educational materials, with the mean of 4.47 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, then The active participation of students and community members who serve to develop a curriculum founded on indigenous people's cultural history, with the mean of 4.37 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Stories, diaries, textbooks, etc., are produced by the indigenous teachers, with the mean of 4.35 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, The active participation of students and community members who serve to develop a curriculum founded on indigenous people's cultural identify with the mean of 4.33 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Non-verbal education materials are produced by the indigenous teachers, got the lowest mean of 4.24 interpreted as Very Satisfactory

For overall mean of 4.48 interpreted as Very Satisfactory with the SD of .570 that the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Indigenous Knowledge System Practices.

Curriculum Content and Planning

In the table 3 extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Curriculum Content and Planning,

Promote positive attitudes to indigenous cultures among the non-indigenous population, to promote understanding, tolerance, and solidarity between different cultural groups got a highest weighted mean of 4.56 interpreted as Outstanding.

Table 3. *The extent of implementation in terms of Curriculum Content and Planning (n=132)*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Are designed with the active involvement of indigenous communities.	4.48	VS
2. Gradually integrate indigenous and western forms of knowledge.	4.44	VS
3. Gradually integrate indigenous and western forms of knowing.	4.42	VS
4. Are place- and culture-based.	4.41	VS
5. Includes seasonal- environmental curricula.	4.32	VS
6. Include the use of local flora.	4.38	VS
7. Include the use of local fauna.	4.36	VS
8. Reflect the interrelation of subjects.	4.39	VS
9. Promote positive attitudes to indigenous languages to promote understanding, tolerance and solidarity between different cultural groups.	4.53	O
10. Promote positive attitudes to indigenous cultures among the non-indigenous population, to promote understanding, tolerance, and solidarity between different cultural groups.	4.56	O
Overall Mean:	4.43	VS

Second to highest is promote positive attitudes to indigenous languages to promote understanding, tolerance and solidarity between different cultural groups with the mean of 4.53 interpreted as Outstanding, design with the active involvement of indigenous communities with the mean of 4.48 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Gradually integrate indigenous and western forms of knowledge, with the mean of 4.44 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Gradually integrate indigenous and western forms of knowing, with the mean of 4.42 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Are place- and culture-based, with the mean of 4.41 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, then Reflect the interrelation of subjects, with the mean of 4.39 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Include the use of local flora, with the mean of 4.38 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Include the use of local fauna with the mean of 4.36 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Includes seasonal- environmental curricula, got the lowest mean of 4.32 interpreted as Very Satisfactory

For overall mean of 4.43 interpreted as Outstanding with the SD of .634 that the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Curriculum Content and Planning.

Language and Instruction

The extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Language and Instruction, Recognizing that language is not only a too; for communication and knowledge but also a fundamental element of cultural identity got a highest weighted mean of 4.62 interpreted as Outstanding, Second to highest is Learning other languages as a basis for cross-cultural understanding and tolerance with the mean of 4.56 interpreted as Outstanding, Teaching and learning indigenous knowledge and curricula through indigenous language and produced material in indigenous languages and Teaching and learning of and through mother tongue in early schooling and literacy instruction with the mean of 4.53 interpreted as Outstanding, Teaching moving on the learning and learning of and through mother tongue moving on to learning other languages in a culturally appropriates and gradual way, according to learners' capacities and needs, with the mean of 4.50 interpreted as Outstanding.

Table 4. *The extent of implementation in terms of Language and Instruction (n=132)*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Recognizing that language is not only a too; for communication and knowledge but also a fundamental element of cultural identity.	4.62	Outstanding
2. Teaching and learning indigenous knowledge and curricula through indigenous language and produced material in indigenous languages.	4.53	Outstanding
3. Teaching and learning indigenous knowledge and curricula through the use of locally researched and produced material in indigenous languages.	4.44	Outstanding
4. Teaching and learning of and through mother tongue in early schooling and literacy instruction.	4.53	Outstanding
5. Teaching moving on the learning and learning of and through mother tongue moving on to learning other languages in a culturally appropriates and gradual way, according to learners' capacities and needs.	4.50	Outstanding
6. Involving native speakers of indigenous languages as teachers.	4.44	Very Satisfactory
7. Learning other languages as a basis for cross-cultural understanding and tolerance	4.56	Outstanding
Total mean	4.52	Outstanding

Teaching and learning indigenous knowledge and curricula through the use of locally researched and produced material in indigenous languages and Involving native speakers of indigenous languages as teachers, got the lowest mean of 4.44 interpreted as Very Satisfactory

For overall mean of 4.52 interpreted as Outstanding with the SD of .615 that the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Language and Instruction

Teacher Training

The extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Teacher Training, Respectful to indigenous concepts and values who are engage in an interactive process with indigenous communities and students got a highest weighted mean of 4.73 interpreted as Outstanding.

Table 5. *The extent of implementation in terms of Teacher Training (n=132)*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. The school has competent and qualified teachers who are:		
2. Familiar with indigenous culture as well as national culture.	4.48	VS
3. Familiar with indigenous language as well as national language.	4.42	VS
4. Respectful to indigenous concepts and values regarding education.	4.67	O
5. Respectful to indigenous concepts and values who are engage in an interactive process with indigenous communities and students.	4.73	O
6. Using and creating responsive and experiential teaching methods in cooperation and consultation with indigenous community.	4.55	O
7. Using and creating responsive and experiential teaching materials in cooperation and consultation with indigenous community.	4.48	VS
8. Trained in bilingual teaching methods.	4.45	VS
9. Trained in language-training methodologies.	4.41	VS
10. Selected in consultation with indigenous communities	4.39	VS
11. Open to continuous assessment of their teaching practices.	4.48	VS
Overall Mean	4.51	O

Second to highest is Respectful to indigenous concepts and values regarding education with the mean of 4.67 interpreted as Outstanding, Using and creating responsive and experiential teaching methods in cooperation and consultation with indigenous community with the mean of 4.55 interpreted as Outstanding Familiar with indigenous culture as well as national culture Using and creating responsive and experiential teaching materials in cooperation and consultation with indigenous community and Open to continuous assessment of their teaching, with the mean of 4.48 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Trained in bilingual teaching methods, with the mean of 4.45 interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

Familiar with indigenous language as well as national language, with the mean of 4.42 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Trained in language-training methodologies, with the mean of 4.41 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Selected in consultation with indigenous communities, got the lowest mean of 4.39 interpreted as Very Satisfactory

For overall mean of 4.51 interpreted as Outstanding with the SD of .528 that the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Teacher Training.

Materials

The extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Materials, Material that promotes an interactive learning – teaching process got a highest weighted mean of 4.42 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, second to highest is Material in indigenous languages and incorporating indigenous knowledge produced with the participation and consent of indigenous communities, teachers and learners with the mean of 4.41 interpreted as Very Satisfactory. Visual, sensual and practical materials for non-verbal communication with the mean of 4.39 interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

Table 6. *The extent of implementation in terms of Materials (n=132)*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. The school make use of and produces innovative and culturally adequate teaching materials based on indigenous and western educational concepts including:		
2. Material based on respect for the cultural values and specific relationship with nature of indigenous communities.	4.32	VS
3. Visual, sensual and practical materials for non-verbal communication.	4.39	VS
4. Material in indigenous languages and incorporating indigenous knowledge produced with the participation and consent of indigenous communities, teachers and learners.	4.41	VS
5. Material that promotes an interactive learning – teaching process.	4.42	VS
6. Material that provides an accurate picture and fair information on indigenous cultures and ways of life.	4.32	VS
Overall Mean	4.37	VS

Material based on respect for the cultural values and specific relationship with nature of indigenous communities and Material that provides an accurate picture and fair information on indigenous cultures and ways of life, got the lowest mean of 4.32 interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

For overall mean of 4.37 interpreted as Very Satisfactory with the SD of .617 that the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Materials.

Assessment and Evaluation

Table 7. The extent of implementation in terms of Assessment and Evaluation (n=132)

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Learning outcomes (in terms of students’ cultural knowledge, practical skills and understanding and their ability to use these in different context): through observation, practical assessment, linking students’ performance at home with that in schools, standardized and norm-based test, when and where appropriate.	4.36	VS
2.	Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through self-assessment.	4.36	VS
3.	Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through participatory research by educators	4.23	VS
4.	Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through observation and review by elders and parents.	4.32	VS
5.	Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through interviewing students and comparing their learning activities in school.	4.32	VS
6.	Teachers’ performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide learning opportunities for students, and well as their competence in regard local and national languages, and their cultural knowledge): through self-assessment	4.29	VS
7.	Teachers; performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide learning opportunities for students, and well as their competence in regard local and national languages, and their cultural knowledge): through the involvement of indigenous communities in selecting, advising, and assessing teachers.	4.27	VS
8.	Teachers; performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide learning opportunities for students, and well as their competence in regard local and national languages, and their cultural knowledge): through the provision of opportunities for teachers to expands their cultural knowledge and pedagogical skills.	4.27	VS
9.	Curriculum (in terms of content, priorities, timing and the interrelation of subjects, based on national as well as cultural standards): through continuous review and redefinition by all educational actors.	4.32	VS
10.	Materials (in terms of their accuracy and appropriateness, in relation to the local cultural context and natural environment): through establishing of review committees in the creation and review of textbooks and other curriculum materials	4.29	VS
	Overall Mean	4.30	VS

In the table 1.7 extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of Assessment and Evaluation, Learning outcomes (in terms of students’ cultural knowledge, practical skills and understanding and their ability to use these in different context): through observation, practical assessment, linking students’ performance at home with that in schools, standardized and norm-based test, when and where appropriate and Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through self-assessment got a highest weighted mean of 4.36 interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

Second to highest is Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through observation and review by elders and parents, Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through interviewing students and comparing their learning activities in school and Curriculum (in terms of content, priorities, timing and the interrelation of subjects, based on national as well as cultural standards): through continuous review and redefinition by all educational actors with the mean of 4.32 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Teachers’ performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide learning opportunities for students, and well as their competence in regard local and national languages, and their cultural knowledge): through self-assessment and Materials (in terms of their accuracy and appropriateness, in relation to the local cultural context and natural environment): through establishing of review committees in the creation and review of textbooks and other curriculum materials , with the mean of 4.29 interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

Teachers; performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide learning opportunities for students, and well as their competence in regard local and national languages, and their cultural knowledge): through the involvement of indigenous communities in selecting, advising, and assessing teachers, and Teachers; performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide learning opportunities for students, and well as their competence in regard local and national languages, and their cultural knowledge): through the provision of opportunities for teachers to expands their cultural knowledge and pedagogical skills with the mean of 4.27 interpreted as Very Satisfactory, Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting student growth, vis-a-vis the national curriculum): through participatory research by educators, got the lowest mean of 4.23 interpreted as Very Satisfactory

For overall mean of 4.30 interpreted as Very Satisfactory with the SD of .724 that the extent of implementation of Indigenous People Education in Sarangani in terms of

Assessment and Evaluation

Key Performance Indicators

Table 8. *Key Performance Indicators of the Indigenous People School*

Indicators	Percentage		
	Male	Female	Total Average
Participation Rate	87.05	87.79	87.33
Enrolment Rate	90.20	90.97	90.3
Cohort Survival Rate	92.70	95.84	89.79
Completion Rate	90.87	93.66	88.50
Promotional Rate	99.12	99.45	99.28
Graduation Rate	97.61	99.44	98.37
Transition Rate	102.89	99.07	99.16
Retention Rate	103.14	99.48	100.45
Drop-Out Rate	0.29	0.09	0.16

In the table 8 key performance indicators of the indigenous people school in terms of participation Rate with the percentage of 87.33%, Enrolment Rate with the percentage of 90.39%. Cohort Survival Rate with the percentage of 89.79%, Completion Rate with the percentage of 88.50%, Promotional Rate with the percentage of 99.28%, Graduation Rate with the percentage of 98.37%, Transition Rate with the percentage of 99.16%, Retention Rate with the percentage of 100.45% and Drop-out Rate with the percentage of 0.16%.

The data reveals that retention rate got the highest percentage, meaning that 100.45% of the school-aged indigenous people learners continue their schooling. It is also supported by the very low dropout rate of the schools.

Table 9. *Extent of Compliance of the School on the Implemented Program Implementation*

Indicators	Percentage	Interpretation
Pedagogy and Methodology	90.20	Very High Level
Indigenous Knowledge and System Practices	89.60	Very High Level
Curriculum Content and Planning	88.60	Very High Level
Language and Instruction	90.40	Very High Level
Teacher Training	90.20	Very High Level
Materials	87.40	Very High Level
Assessment and Evaluation	86.00	Very High Level
Total average	88.91	Very High Level

In the table 3 extent of compliance of the school on the implemented program implementation in terms of Language and Instruction, got a highest percentage of 90.40 interpreted as Very High Level, Second to highest is Pedagogy and Methodology and Teacher Training with the mean of 90.20 interpreted as Very High Level, Indigenous Knowledge System Practices with the mean of 89.60 interpreted as Very High Level, Curriculum Content and Planning, with the mean of 88.60 interpreted as Very High Level, Materials with the mean of 87.40 interpreted as Very High Level, Assessment and Evaluation, got the lowest mean of 86.00 interpreted as Very High Level.

Relationship Between the Extent of Program Implementation and the Key Performance Indicators

As Presented in Table 5, significant relationship between the extent of program implementation and the key performance indicators four indicators of key performance showed less than p-values of 0.05, Participation Rate ($r = 0.212, p = 0.015^*$), Cohort Survival Rate ($r = 0.211, p = 0.015^*$), Completion Rate ($r = 0.196, p = 0.024^*$), and Drop-out Rate ($r = -0.217, p = 0.012^*$), to extent of program implementation is significant at significance level of 0.05 and the null hypothesis is rejected that implies there is significant relationship between the extent of program implementation and the key performance indicators.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship Between the Extent of Program Implementation and the Key Performance Indicators*

Variables	extent of program implementation			
	r - value	p - value	Remarks	Decision
Key performance indicators				
Participation Rate	0.212	0.015*	Significant	Reject Ho
Enrolment Rate	-0.158	0.071	Not significant	Do not reject HO
Cohort Survival Rate	0.211	0.015*	significant	Reject Ho
Completion Rate	0.196	0.024*	Significant	Reject Ho
Promotional Rate	0.005	0.955	Not significant	Do not reject HO
Graduation Rate	0.084	0.339	Not significant	Do not reject HO
Transition Rate	0.081	0.358	Not significant	Do not reject HO
Retention Rate	-0.014	0.870	Not significant	Do not reject HO
Drop-out Rate	-0.217	0.012*	Significant	Reject Ho

Conclusions

All the indicators on the extent of implementation: Pedagogy and Methodology, Indigenous Knowledge System Practices Curriculum Content and Planning, Language and Instruction, Teacher Training, Materials, Assessment and Evaluation got a total mean of 4.45 and described as very satisfactory in terms on implementation, meaning this indicates that the program component is in high level of implementation.

Among all the performance indicators, retention rate got the highest percentage, meaning that 100.45% of the school-aged indigenous people learners continue their schooling. It is also supported by the very low dropout rate of the schools at 0.16%

The school's execution of the programs is remarkable, as is demonstrated by the way it incorporates community practices, indigenous knowledge, and language into teaching students. The majority of the time, schools contextualize the content and teachings to suit the requirements and interests of the students. Even so, there are several areas that could use improvement, particularly in the areas of assessment and evaluation.

The best practices the school head did was to designate of IP teachers to Key Stage 1 Level, Contextualization of Materials/Community-based examples, Non IP teachers adopts the IP language, Celebration of IP Day, integration of IKSPs in the contextualization of lessons, Inclusion of IPED implementation in the SIP/ AIP, Participation/Involvement of Elders, Parents, and Culture Bearers, Use of mother tongue in lesson delivery, retooling on IPED framework and Use of local materials. The challenges they have encountered are mismatched of teachers, language barriers and financial concerns while the coping mechanism that the school did was collaborate with the member of the community, peer mentoring and partnership with stakeholders

Statistics shows that the participation rate, cohort survival rate, completion rate, and dropout rate of the implementing schools has a significant relationship by the extent of implementation of the indigenous people's education program.

Future studies to be conducted may utilize larger sample size so that it would be ensured that the entire population of a specific community or area will be well-represented. Other studies may also be conducted in some places in the country and the results may be compared to the outcomes of this research.

This study only utilized quantitative approach, which is also one of the delimitations and weaknesses of this research, future studies may also include a qualitative interview to support and strengthen the quantitative findings.

References

- Abayao, L. (2014). The Philippines indigenous peoples' core curriculum. UP Forum. Retrieved from <http://www.up.edu.ph/the-philippines-indigenous-peoples-core-curriculum/>.
- Agorilla, Y. T. (2015). Development and validation of an inquiry based learning module on science investigatory 1 for grade 7 students. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Philippine Normal University North Luzon Campus, Isabela.
- Aguinaldo Jr., C., & Domingo, A. (2021). Design, development and implementation of contextualized learning materials in grade 7 mathematics. *Academia Letters*, Article 1468. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL1468>.
- Alata, E. J. P. (2019). Evaluation of outcomes-based private junior high school English curricula. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 11(1), 43-64.
- Albert, J. R. G., & David, C. C. (2012). Primary education: Barriers to entry and bottlenecks to completion (No. 2012-07). PIDS Discussion Paper Series.
- Albert, J. R. G., Orbeta Jr., A. C., Paqueo, V. B., Serafica, R. B., Dadios, E. P., Culaba, A. B., ... & Bairan, J. C. A. C. (2018). Harnessing government's role for the Fourth Industrial Revolution. PIDS Policy Notes, No. 2018-14. Quezon City, Philippines: Philippine Institute for Development Studies. <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidspn1814.pdf> (accessed on January 28, 2023).
- Ardington, C., Wills, G., & Kotze, J. (2021). COVID-19 learning losses: Early grade reading in South Africa. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 86, 102480.
- Bartle. (2017). Research and public management. UP Open University: Diliman, Quezon City.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1986). Ecology of the family as a context for human development: Research perspectives. *Developmental Psychology*, 22(6), 723.
- Brown-Jeffy, S., & Cooper, J. E. (2011). Toward a conceptual framework of culturally relevant pedagogy: An overview of the conceptual and theoretical literature. *Teacher Education Quarterly*.
- Brush, S. B., & Stabinsky, D. (1996). Valuing local knowledge: Indigenous people and intellectual property rights. Island Press.
- Crowe, S., Cresswell, K., Robertson, A., Huby, G., Avery, A., & Sheikh, A. (2011). The case study approach. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 11(1), 1-9.

- Cullinane, M. (2009). Bringing in the brigands: The politics of pacification in the colonial Philippines, 1902-1907. *Philippine Studies*, 49-76.
- David, C., & Albert, J. R. G. (2015). How has basic education in the Philippines fared and what else needs to be done? *PIDS Policy Notes*, 8.
- David, C. C., & Albert, J. R. G. (2015). Recent trends in out-of-school children in the Philippines. *PIDS Discussion Paper*, No. 2015-51. https://dirp3.pids.gov.ph/websitcms/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1551_rev2.pdf (accessed on January 28, 2023).
- David, C. C., Albert, J. R. G., & Vizmanos, J. F. V. (2018). Boys are still left behind in basic education. *PIDS Discussion Paper Series*.
- Dekker, D., & Young, C. (2005). Bridging the gap: The development of appropriate educational strategies for minority language communities.
- Department Order No. 32, s. 2015. Adopting the indigenous peoples education curriculum framework. Retrieved from <http://www.deped.gov.ph/press-releases/depedissuesiped-curriculum-framework>.
- DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011. The National Indigenous Peoples Education Policy Framework.
- DepEd Order No. 22, 2016. Indigenous People Education Program Implementation.
- DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2022. Adoption of the Basic Education Development Plan 2030.
- Donnelly, R., & Patrinos, H. A. (2021). Learning loss during COVID-19: An early systematic review. *Prospects*, 1-9.
- Dupere, K. (2016). 5 educational hurdles Indigenous children face around the world. <http://mashable.com/2016/08/08/indigenous-education-inequality/#jywl2iix3mqb6>.
- Eduardo, J. P., & Gabriel, A. G. (2021). Indigenous peoples and the right to education: The Dumagat experience in the provinces of Nueva Ecija and Aurora, Philippines. *SAGE Open*, 11(2), 21582440211009491.
- Education International's Response to the Global Monitoring Report 2011. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://download.ei-ie.org/Docs/WebDepot/EI_GMR2011_Analysis_EN.pdf.
- EFA. (2015). Philippine Education for All. Philippine Development Plan 2017-2022. https://www.academia.edu/34768288/Philippine_Development_Plan_PDP_2017-2022.
- Felder, R. M., & Spurlin, J. (2005). Applications, reliability, and validity of the Index of Learning Styles. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 21(1), 103-112.
- Gu, Y., & Warren, J. (2017). Methods for descriptive studies. *Handbook of eHealth Evaluation*.
- Hughes, E. M. (2011). The effects of the concrete-representational-abstract sequenced instruction on struggling learners acquisition, retention, and self-efficacy of fraction. Dissertation, Graduate School of Clemson University.
- Kraay, A. (2019). The World Bank human capital index: A guide. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 34(1), 1-33.
- Lumapenet, H. (2017). Influence of the family on the pupils' reading performance. Unpublished research.
- Mei-Zhao, C., & Kuh, G. (2004, March). Adding value: Learning communities and student engagement. *Springer Link*, 45(2), 115-138. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/B:RIHE.0000015692.88534>.
- Misquitta, R. (2011). Teaching fractions to middle-school students struggling in mathematics: An exploratory study. Doctoral Dissertation, University of Texas, USA.
- Mokoena, S. (2011). Participative decision-making: Perceptions of school stakeholders.
- Morales, M. P. E. (2014). Culture and language sensitive physics on student concept attainment. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*.
- Moscoviz, L., & Evans, D. K. (2022). Learning loss and student dropouts during the COVID-19 pandemic: A review of the evidence two years after schools shut down. Center for Global Development, Working Paper, 609.
- Olumorin, C. O., Yusuf, A., Ajidagba, U. A., & Jekayinfa, A. A. (2010). Development of instructional materials from local resources for art-based courses. *Asian Journal of Information Technology*, 9(2), 107-110.
- Pasco, F. P. (2019). The level of SBM implementation in relation to school performance indicators: Basis for effective administrative planning. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(2L).
- Perin, D. (2011). Facilitating student learning through contextualization: A review of evidence. *Community College Review*, 39(3), 268-295.

- Philippine Education For All 2015: Implementation and challenges. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/sites/default/files/ressources/philippines_efa_mda.pdf.
- Psacharopoulos, G., & Patrinos, H. (1994). Indigenous people and poverty in Latin America.
- Quentin, W., & Cosentino, G. (2019, August 7). Education for global development. World Bank. <https://worldbank.org/>.
- Republic Act No. 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education of 2013: Implementing Rules and Regulations.
- Republic Act No. 9155. (2001). An act instituting a framework of governance for basic education.
- Reuge, N., Jenkins, R., Brossard, M., Soobrayan, B., Mizunoya, S., Ackers, J., ... & Taulo, W. G. (2021). Education response to COVID 19 pandemic, a special issue proposed by UNICEF: Editorial review. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 87, 102485.
- Rural, J. D. (2021). Competency in assessment of selected DepEd teachers in National Capital Region. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 10(4), pp-639.
- Shore, M., Shore, J., & Boggs, S. (2004). Allied health applications integrated into developmental mathematics using problem-based learning. *Mathematics and Computer Education*, 38, 183-189.
- Smith, G. H. (2003). Indigenous struggle for the transformation of education. In *Alaskan Federation of Natives Convention*, Anchorage, Alaska.
- Stufflebeam, D. L. (1983). The CIPP model for program evaluation. In *Evaluation models* (pp. 117-141). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Ty, R. (2010). Indigenous peoples in the Philippines: Continuing struggle. *Focus Asia-Pacific*, 62, 6-9.
- UNESCO. (1990). *World Declaration on Education for All*. Paris: UNESCO.
- UNICEF. (2021). *The State of the Global Education Crisis: A Path to Recovery*.
- University of Washington Center for Educational Leadership. (2014). *Creating a theory of action for improving teaching and learning*.
- UNESCO. (2000). *Education for All. Status and Trends 2000: Assessing Learning Achievement*, International Consultative Forum on Education for All. Paris: UNESCO. Retrieved January 15, 2009, from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0011/001198/119823e.pdf>
- UNESCO. (2000). *Dakar Framework for Action: Education for All. Meeting Our Collective Commitments*. World Forum on Education, Dakar, Senegal, 26-28 April 2000, UNESCO, Paris.
- UNESCO. (2001). *International Conference on Education 46th Session: Final Report*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Utech, J. L. (2013). *Contextualized curriculum for workplace education: An introductory guide*. Retrieved from <https://www.umass.edu/roundtable/projects>.
- Villaplaza, L. (2021). Level of Implementation of Indigenous Peoples Education Program in Agusan Del Sur, Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Contemporary Education and Communication Technology*, 7(1).
- Vygotsky, Lev Semenovich. (1972). The psychology of art. *Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism*, 30(4).
- Weaver, H. N. (1999). Indigenous people and the social work profession: Defining culturally competent services. *Social Work*, 44(3), 217-225.
- Weiss, C. H. (1998). *Methods for studying programs and policies*. Wiki-Devel. Sugarlabs.Org.
- World Bank. (2021). *World Bank East Asia and Pacific Economic Update, Spring 2021: Uneven Recovery*.
- Yagci, F. (2010). *The Effect of Instruction with Concrete Models on Eight Grade Students' Probability Achievement and Attitudes toward Probability*. (Thesis), Middle East Technical University, Turkey.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Edward Ryan F. Gulam, PhD

Department of Education – Philippines

Alma S. Hordista, PhD

Notre Dame of Dadiangas University – Philippines